

Nature and Man

Norboyev Abduvali Ovlaqulovich

Ph.D., Department of "Principles of Spirituality and Legal Education", Faculty of History, Tashkent State Pedagogical University

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Sep 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Oct 2024; **Published:** 22 Nov 2024

Abstract: in this article, the influence of natural phenomena on human activity, the lack of attention paid by social sciences in the study of these effects, as well as the dangers that may occur due to the increase of anthropogenic influence in the process of using nature and its resources. Uzbekistan, the Central Asian region, as well as the international level are shown and their solutions are discussed.

Keywords: nature, natural phenomena, religious views, natural resources, anthropogenic factors, emergency situations, climate migration, climate change, food shortage, global problems, etc.

It is known that throughout the past, mankind has suffered and fought against the vagaries of nature, as well as various natural phenomena, disasters and catastrophes. That is why people have tried to anticipate their occurrence, prevent them and reduce the damage caused by them.

Many events in history are known to cause harm to mankind. However, their causes and socio-economic effects have not yet been systematically studied. In particular, the negative impact of various infectious diseases on humans, animals and plants, causing severe consequences, many examples of material culture created by mankind, the destruction of cities and villages, the crisis of various civilizations, economic impoverishment, Almost no information is found in the science of history about the reason for the premature death of millions of people.

In order to ensure their safety and peace, people have tried to protect themselves from various events occurring in nature or to reduce their negative consequences. These movements led to the emergence of different religious views, and later scientific approaches. In particular, the fact that the whole life of primitive people depended on the whims of nature and their inability to fight against them, as well as the fear of the spontaneous events of nature, which were a constant companion, led to the emergence of religious views ¹. As a result of historical development, protection from natural phenomena and the fight against its consequences have caused great changes in human life, the formation of unique values, ²the emergence of scientific views and their materialization.

In history, the first political system, that is, the union of tribes, and then the emergence of states, in a certain sense, determined the relationship of mankind to nature. Of course, during these periods, special state agencies were not established to prevent and eliminate the consequences of various disasters and accidents. However, these tasks are assigned to other structures of the state.

¹ Joraev U., Saidjonov Y. The world religions history - Tashkent : East, 1998. – B. 21.

²In that place. – B. 21

In today's terms, protection from such emergency situations has been implemented by our ancestors since ancient times. This has led to the emergence of many values in our land. In particular, it is possible to feel how necessary the ideas put forward in the book "Avesta" and some traditions used in the way of life are for today. It was these thoughts that reflected the fact that nature is the most important factor in ensuring human life, its peaceful and prosperous life.

In the book, the struggle between Ahura Mazda, the god of goodness, and Ahriman, the god of death and evil, is explained in connection with natural phenomena. For example, Ahura Mazda created the second "realm" Sogd. "Ahriman, whose entire being is mixed with death, came and created Sakayatya, who belongs to the race of stars. He spread the seed of death to the whole herd³. " And Ahura Mazda created "Marv", "Ahriman" created the "ant", "Ahura Mazda" created "Balkh", "Ahriman" came and created "the locust that dries grass and grain with greatness."⁴ It can be seen that the ants and locust swarms caused great damage to the agriculture and animal husbandry of the inhabitants of the above-mentioned area.

In Zoroastrianism, it is shown to be very careful with water, earth, fire, mountains and glaciers, as well as the animal world, which are the factors of human existence. Keeping them clean was considered an important factor in human survival. Even anyone who violated the rules of conserving water, fire, earth and air was punished with beatings.

For example, in Zoroastrianism, in order to maintain the purity of the water, it is strictly forbidden to spit, cast a stick, or throw anything else into it. Those who did not follow this were punished. In "Avesta" it is forbidden to wash clothes, feed cattle, tie camels and horses, perform ablution by water sources.

Islam, which appeared in the lives of Asian peoples after Zoroastrianism, with its ideas about how important natural factors are in the lives of people, as well as the fact that natural phenomena led to the extinction of certain peoples there are many evidences about the arrival. In short, both religions glorify qualities such as purity, purity, and moderation. However, these are the main factors in the development of any society.

Historical sources have enough information about natural phenomena and their dramatic effects on human life, but it seems that they have not been systematically analyzed historically. In particular, there are reports of earthquakes and their terrible consequences in the regions of Central Asia. In particular, the social impact of information about earthquakes in the territory of our country can be found in Abu Saeed Gardizi's "Kitobi Zainal Akhbar", Khorasan historian Juwaini's "History of Jahangir Genghis Khan", Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Baburnoma", Muhammad Tahir ibn Abdul Qasim's "Amazing Tabaqot" ", in the book "Security service in the reign of Amir Temur" by the historian scientist H. Sodikov and others can be seen.

Further human activities, i.e. the increase in the need for industrial production, the emergence of commodity-money relations, the growth of the demand for raw materials and a number of other factors lead to the victory of the states in the competition in the political and economic spheres. a sharp increase in anthropogenic impact on nature due to aspiration ; the economic, political and ideological hegemony of the former socialist and capitalist system , the emergence of independent states; the development of the arms race, that is, the production of nuclear, chemical and bacteriological weapons, and other activities can be seen. This human activity and their central position in world politics has also led to an increase in their negative influence on the human world.

According to UN data, in the 60s of the 20th century, those who suffered from emergency

³A soldier Strong translation. Avesta is historical-eternal memorial – Tashkent : East, 2001, – B. 123.

⁴Hamidov H. Avesta interest - Tashkent : A. Qadiri in the name of people heritage , 2001, – B. 67.

situations made up 1.6% of the world's population, and by the 1980s, it increased to 3.5%⁵. In the last quarter of this century, 3.5 million people died from natural disasters. people died, 3 billion. More than 1,000 people were injured⁶. Past of the century last years different disasters as a result death those who have the number 6 per year % to grow up went⁷ Or in Brussels Accidents according to scientific research of the center information according to next three ten annually natural from disasters the world 14 according to million person death reached General economic loss 400 billion . USA dollar organize reached If passed different in the 60s and 70s of the century natural and man-made in color extraordinary from situations from an average of 62 people one person injured by the year 2000, it will be from every 55 people one person began⁸to organize .

Next ten in in the world happened giving different economic crises and financial declines are also to nature anthropogenic of influence increased to go with is being explained . Including the UN the world food program information look when you throw , the world Food in 2011 price 25% more expensive . To this reason divisor main factor economy and ecological that environment is being evaluated . Boz over the last 40 years during village economy products in cultivation anthropogenic of technologies application due to in the world fertile of lands from three one part invalid to the situation come the rest

Another one factor – industry work release and in cities urbanization level increase village economy products for water spending to decrease take is coming⁹And this cross-border from rivers using countries between also strong in relationships effect is doing Especially some of years arid coming food of products decreased to go , the world across food products of the price increase in price , as well as desertification of the process the increase is also ecological in color of disasters face to give and food shortage risk to increase reason is happening

UN 2015 Japan like you in the city being past Natural disasters risk reduce regarding the third International at the conference During 2005-2015 natural 700,000 disasters person to death , 1.5 billion person's 1.4 bln . person's damage reason that it was confession done Here again at the conference natural disasters the world countries 1.3 trillion US dollars to the economy in the amount damage also in 2008-2012 natural disasters of 144 million people to move take the arrival note done¹⁰ That's it because of , authoritative international organizations , military blocks are also their own activity direction change it started States between in relationships extraordinary of situations prevention get and consequences reduce such as issues political to the scene come out started

by the UN conducted this conference and in it acceptance done events different natural of disasters prevention get and of them protection measures increase the world countries in front of standing important from work one that shows . This to the period IAEA under the UN , World health storage organization and environment save with depends has been of structures formation , different of programs acceptance to be done , as well as some for days international color it is also given is proof . Including this each October 13 of the year " Natural of disasters prevention get International day ", April 22 " Earth day to be called and international scale being conducted events see also example can

In fact , it is a global trend received this processes just now developed coming young

⁵ Kol .a vtor . Zashita Naselenia i territorial the horse chrezvychaynyx situ a tsi yah , - Tashkent : IGZ, 2003. – S. 9.

⁶in that place , – V. 11.

⁷in that place , – V. 11.

⁸ Sergeev I., Preduprejdeni e chrezvychaynyx situatsional bro odin element eco-friendly bezopasnoti "Ekologicheskaya". safety i hrajdanskaya initiative ", 2005, #6, – S. 9.

⁹Abdulbaqiev F., One seeing thought do it // XX I ASR, – 2012, 19 April . 16-(440)- number

¹⁰Protocols of the Third World Conference OON po snijeniyu riska bedstvii. Sendai-Japan . 2015, – S. 15-16. / [https://www.unisdr.org/files/45069\(05.12.2020\)](https://www.unisdr.org/files/45069(05.12.2020))

independent excluding countries, including Uzbekistan did not pass. To this, one from the side, far time during of the republic economic in development extensive of the method negative consequences reason has been if, the second on the global scale being observed anthropogenic factor under the influence of man-made changes ecology deterioration take came

It is known that at the end of the 20th century, specific state bodies and systems were formed in 128 countries specifically for emergency situations. In particular, in the first years of independence, Uzbekistan felt the need for a special state system to prepare for and prevent natural and man-made disasters. There were a number of natural, man-made and environmental reasons for the formation of such a state system in the Republic. That is, at that time, 60% of the republic's population lived in areas prone to landslides and flooding, and 80% of the population (15 million people) lived in areas prone to 7-point earthquakes¹¹. These are while in the republic chemical poisonous substances and radioactive damage with depends to increase the risks take coming can Including Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and of Uzbekistan mountainous in the regions located, large in quantity water to the size have 315 the lakes seismic actions during own from the situation out leaving and them correct can't be consequences take to arrive risk increases.

As a result of strong anthropogenic influences from the second half of the last century, water shortage began to occur in the Aral Sea, and as a result, the Orolkum desert appeared in this area in the following years. The measures taken to alleviate the situation in the archipelago regions affect not only the situation in Uzbekistan or the countries of the region, but also the atmosphere and climate of the world.

In general, emergency situations that threaten the countries of the region, as well as Uzbekistan, can be divided into the following types. To them:

- ✓ location in a seismically active zone;
- ✓ natural, man-made and ecological emergency situations related to water;
- ✓ landslides and displacements;
- ✓ radiation hazard;
- ✓ epizootic, epiphytotic and zoonosis conditions;
- ✓ air and environmental pollution;
- ✓ circumstances related to the development, storage, transportation and use of highly toxic substances;
- ✓ all kinds of man-made emergencies, etc.

It is worth noting that a number of factors, such as unreasonable use of natural resources, lack of common culture in the use of man-made layers, failure to use the results of existing scientific research under humanistic ideas, surround the entire humanity with irreparable dangers. is taking These risks are:

- insufficient use of natural resources for future generations;
- climate change and related water shortages, desertification, depletion of natural food products;
- increased energy demand;

¹¹UzMA, M - Fund 37, list 1, Case 132, 1-vara q

- population migration to the northern regions, i.e. to countries located on the water's edge, as a result of increased climate migration, and the growth of problems related to them;
- consists of global problems such as excessive pollution of air, water and soil.

actions in preventing the risks associated with these situations is, first of all, to improve relations between countries, to establish mutual agreements on the prevention of these situations arising at the international level, etc.

References:

1. Joraev U., Saidjonov Y. The world religions history. -Tashkent: East, 1998.
2. A soldier Strong translation. Avesta is historical-eternal memorial – Tashkent : East, 2001, – B. 123.
3. Hamidov H. Avesta interest - Tashkent : A. Qadiri in the name of people heritage , 2001
4. Kol .a vtor . Zashita Naselenia i territorial the horse chrezvychnykh situ a tsi yah , - Thank you : IGZ, 2003
5. Sergeev I., Preduprejdeni e chrezvychnykh situatsional bro odin element eco-friendly bezopasnoti "Ekologicheskaya". safety i hrajdanskaya initiative ", 2005, #6,
6. Abdulbaqiev F., One seeing thought do it // XXI ASR, – 2012, 19 April. 16-(440)- number
7. Protocols of the Third World Conference OON po snijeniyu riska bedstvii. Sendai-Japan . 2015, – S. 1516. / https://www.unisdr.org/files/45069_05.12.2020)
8. UzMA, M - Fund 37, list 1, Case 132, 1-vara q
9. Oglu, Abduganiev Ozod Tursunboy. "Pedagogical Conditions And Mechanisms Of Development Of Social Active Civil Competence In Students." *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education* 12.7 (2021): 433-442.
10. Abduganiyev O. DEVELOPING STUDENTS'GENERAL HUMAN VALUES COMPETENCY IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN EDUCATION CONDITIONS //Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 10. – С. 190-194.
11. OT, AbdugʻAniyev. "YANGI O ʻZBEKISTON IJTIMOIIY TARAQQIYOTIDA TALABA-YOSHLARNI UMUMINSONIY QADRIYATLARGA OID KOMPETENTLILIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Science and innovation* 3.Special Issue 41 (2024): 281-285.
12. AbdugʻAniyev O. T. TALABALARDA UMUMINSONIY QADRIYATLARGA OID KOMPETENTLILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH MAZMUN-MOHIIYATI //Science and innovation. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. Special Issue 35. – С. 290-295.
13. Абдуғаниев О. Т. Ў. ЯНГИ ЎЗБЕКТИСТОН ШАРОИТИДА ТАЛАБАЛАРДА УМУМИНСОНИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРГА ОИД КOMPETENTЛИЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ //Science and innovation. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. Special Issue 16. – С. 365-369.
14. Абдуғаниев, Озод Турсунбой Ўғли. "ТАЛАБАЛАРДА УМУМИНСОНИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРГА ОИД КOMPETENTЛИЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ МОХИЯТИ ВА МАНТИҚИЙ ЖИХАТДАН ТАХЛИЛИ." *Science and innovation* 3.Special Issue 22 (2024): 351-356.
15. AbdugʻAniyev, O. T. "YANGI O ʻZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA TALABALARDA UMUMINSONIY QADRIYATLARGA OID KOMPETENTLIKNI

RIVOJLANTIRISHGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI PEDAGOGIK HAMKORLIK OMILLARI." *Science and innovation 2*.Special Issue 12 (2023): 52-56.

16. Абдуғаниев О. Т. ТАЛАБАЛАРДА ИЖТИМОЙ ФАОЛ ФУҚАРОЛИК КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 13. – С. 25-29.
17. Tursunboyevich O. A. Pedagogical and psychological opportunities for the development of social active civil competences in students //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 3. – С. 1888-1897.